

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

КРИМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ПРЕСТУПНОСТИ НЕСОВЕРШЕННОЛЕТНИХ

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CRIMINOLOGICAL FEATURES OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается криминологическая характеристика преступности несовершеннолетних; возрастные особенности лиц, не достигших возраста 18 лет, влияющие на преступную направленность их поведения. Изучаются специфические черты преступности несовершеннолетних, а также статистические показатели, отражающие структуру преступности по возрастным характеристикам.

Abstract

The article deals with the criminological characteristics of juvenile delinquency; age characteristics of persons under the age of 18, influencing the criminal orientation of their behavior. The specific features of juvenile delinquency are studied, as well as statistical indicators that reflect the structure of crime by age characteristics.

Ключевые слова: преступность, подросток, особенность, возрастные особенности, групповая преступность, латентность, личность преступника.

Keywords: crime, teenager, peculiarity, age characteristics, gang crime, latency, criminal personality.

Teenagers and young people are characterized by increased criminal activity (if we mean "ordinary" crime, not "white-collar" crime). At the same time, as it is commonly believed, they are the future of any country, and the fate of society and the state depends on their habitual behavior, lifestyle, and personal qualities. Therefore, it is not surprising that so much attention is paid to juvenile delinquency in domestic and foreign literature - criminological, sociological, psychological, pedagogical. Although the important role of adolescents and young people for the future of the country is a fact, as well as their increased criminal activity, this problem is not so simple and clear.

Adults' relatively negative assessment of the behavior of children, adolescents, and young adults has been observed throughout human history. The "conflict of generations" is not unique to modern history. The older generations are always dissatisfied with the younger ones, and the younger ones reciprocate.

Juvenile delinquency (juvenile crime) - an independent type of crime, which represents the totality of crimes and persons (aged 14-18) who committed them in a certain territory in a certain period with quantitative and qualitative characteristics.

From a criminological point of view, it is reasonable to distinguish three age groups in juvenile delinquency: 14-15 years, 15-16 years, and 17-18 years.

In the last decade there has been a process of rejuvenation of criminality. The criminal activity of 14-15 year olds is growing faster than that of 16-17 year olds.

In the structure of juvenile criminality, mercenary and mercenary-violent crimes predominate.

According to the scientist E.S. Zhigarev, the dominant motives of criminal behavior of male minors are selfish motives - 52% (females - 41%); self-assertion -

28%; hooligan motives - 18% (females - 22.6%). Female juveniles identified dependence on adults as a motive for criminal behavior in 16%, financial difficulties in the family in 14% (selfish motive in 55%), and revenge in 6.3% [1,30].

Juvenile delinquency is mostly of a group nature. In some cases, the criminal activity of minors becomes the main way of spending their free time, in connection with which the criminal professionalism of juvenile delinquents increases.

Juvenile delinquency is situational in nature, depending on the prevailing circumstances, due to the peculiarities of the age psyche of minors, their easy propensity to commit crimes.

Indicators of criminalization of minors are the level of administrative offenses, deviant behavior, prevalence of alcoholism, drug addiction, vagrancy. There has been an increase in the number of crimes committed by both male and female minors due to alcoholism, drug abuse and drug addiction.

The negative trend in juvenile crime is characterized by the fact that it is growing much faster than the total number of people in this age group. Against the background of the continuing decline in the birth rate in Russia, these indicators look threatening.

Adolescents are characterized by increased victimization and often become potential victims themselves.

The young generation is naturally characterized by increased activity, which manifests itself in both negative (relatively high criminalization, drug addiction, sexual deviations) and positive (artistic, technical, scientific creativity) manifestations of deviance. Children, adolescents, young people have a high energy, the de-

sire to "discover" or do something new, previously unknown, to assert themselves in innovative activities. But everything has its price. The search leads to creative achievements and to negative deviations, including crime. And children, adolescents, young people die more often than they "should" according to their age (high victimization) [2].

Doctor of Law, Professor V.V. Kukharuk believes that there is a trend of rejuvenation of juvenile delinquency, an increase in criminal activity of younger children, there is a significant increase in female juvenile delinquency. There is an increase in crimes committed by both male and female minors due to alcohol, drug abuse and drug addiction. There is a trend towards the rejuvenation of "drunken" crime: every fifth crime is committed by minors under the influence of alcohol or drugs.

Juvenile delinquency is characterized by a high degree of latency. Moreover, due to the peculiarities of the legal and physical situation of minors and their personal characteristics, statistical indicators of juvenile crime are more "regulated" in investigative and judicial practice. In fact, the prevalence of crimes committed by minors is many times higher than their registered share. Theft, robbery, and hooliganism are particularly prevalent.

Criminological characteristics of the personal traits of juvenile delinquents. Due to the nature of juvenile delinquency in the first place in the study of this phenomenon is the problem of the personality of the offender. The success of the preventive activity of law enforcement bodies depends to a great extent on the extent and depth of the study of the juvenile delinquent's personality. Many mistakes could have been avoided if the law enforcement bodies had always put the personality, and not only the conditions of his life or other influences on it, in the center of their attention and professional efforts. This is fully applicable to juvenile delinquents.

The main thing when considering the personality of a juvenile delinquent is age. It is connected with certain biological, psychological and mental changes in the structure of personality.

Age-related personality change is neither causally nor unambiguously related to the dynamics of basic life relations. The preservation of the basic relations of life is connected with the change of personality in the course of life under the influence of events, circumstances, etc. In addition to chronological age, there is a distinction between psychological, educational and physical age, which do not coincide with each other, which leads to internal conflicts of personality, which can be criminogenic. In general, the so-called "average statistical age" does not really exist. General laws of adolescence manifest themselves in individual variations that depend not only on the environment and the conditions of upbringing, but also on the peculiarities of the organism or personality.

In determining the age characteristics of offenders, criminologists usually divide juveniles into the following groups:

- 14-15 years old - juvenile group;
- 16-17 years old - juveniles.

Criminological, sociological and psychological features of the behavior of the contingent in the age interval 14-17 years show that the behavior of adolescents in this age group is influenced both by the conditions of their life and upbringing in previous years and by "young adults". Hence, the conclusion that juvenile delinquency should be considered in the context of delinquency of persons under 14 and persons over 17.

When analyzing the personalities of juvenile and adult criminals, we can talk about their similarities. The boundary that defines the difference between criminals of different ages essentially disappears when we talk about two age groups: 16-17-year-olds and 18-20-year-olds. In this case, it is quite acceptable to talk about a single age group if we use the concept of incomplete majority.

The majority of juvenile delinquents are males. This is explained, first of all, by the difference in the social relations of the sexes with the environment in which the personality develops, the conditions of moral formation of the personality, the difference in the nature and correlation of typical conflict situations. Predominance of male juvenile delinquents is connected with mental and psychological peculiarities of sex, historically established difference in behavior and upbringing of boys and girls, with greater activity, entrepreneurial spirit and other general characteristic features of men.

In the legal literature the relation between the level of education and the personality of the perpetrator is often pointed out. On the basis of this attribute it is possible to judge the potential capabilities of the personality of a juvenile offender in the performance of his social functions, which to some extent depend on the level of his culture, interests. Speaking about the level of education of juvenile delinquents, it should be noted that it is lower than that of their peers who have not committed a crime. Thus, among juvenile delinquents there are often repeaters who have dropped out of schools, vocational schools, and some - from secondary schools.

From a criminological point of view, the study of the family situation of juvenile delinquents is of particular importance. This is quite understandable, since it is in the family that the socially significant characteristics of the personality and the criteria of its evaluation are formed. Studies show that more than two-thirds of juvenile delinquents grew up in families where quarrels, scandals, mutual insults, drunkenness and debauchery were constantly present. One out of every eight to ten repeat offenders who began a life of crime at an early age was led to drink and crime by parents, older brothers, and close relatives. In addition, a dysfunctional family has a negative influence not only on its own members, but also on other teenagers with whom their children are friends. Thus, there is a process of "contamination" of adolescents who do not directly belong to the family.

The peculiarities of their legal consciousness are not unimportant for the characterization of the personality of juvenile delinquents. Juvenile delinquents are characterized by a profound lack of legal consciousness, which is to some extent explained by two factors: general legal illiteracy (both of the population as a whole and of minors) and negative social experience of

juveniles. The lack of legal awareness of minors who commit crimes is expressed in a negative attitude to legal norms, unwillingness to comply with the requirements of these norms. Significant gaps in the legal knowledge of minors lead to arguments about the "unfairness" of laws, "illegal" conviction.

The social environment of juvenile offenders is also characteristic. Most of them are previously convicted persons who abuse alcohol and drugs.

The problem of free time is a special one. Juvenile delinquents have two to three times more free time than their law-abiding peers. At the same time, according to the results of some studies, as the amount of free time increases, the interests of juveniles become distorted and acquire a negative connotation. Moreover, the more free time there is, the greater the likelihood of delinquency.

The above-mentioned personal characteristics of juvenile delinquents are mainly expressed in the motivation of their criminal behavior. Its main signs:

- Predominance of "childish" motives - committing a crime out of mischief, curiosity, desire to assert oneself in the eyes of peers, desire to possess fashionable things, etc;
- Situational motives;
- Deformation of any element of the sphere of needs, interests, aspirations. For example, hypertrophied understanding of comradeship, striving to increase one's prestige.

Causes and Conditions of Juvenile Delinquency. The causes and conditions of juvenile delinquency, as well as crime in general, are socially determined. They depend primarily on the specific historical conditions of society, the content and orientation of its institutions, the nature and ways of resolving major contradictions.

It is widely believed that the main causes of juvenile delinquency and its rapid growth are the sharp deterioration of the economic situation and the increased tension in society. Of course, all this affects adult crime as well, but the rapid decline in the standard of living affects juveniles the most, because juveniles have always been and still are the most vulnerable part of society. Their vulnerability lies in the fact that the peculiarities of minors (unstable psyche, not fully formed system of values) make them more susceptible to the influence of factors that adults resist much more successfully. Unable to satisfy their needs legally, many juveniles begin to "make money" and obtain the necessary things and products as best they can, often by committing a crime. Minors are actively involved in extortion, illegal businesses, and other types of criminal activity.

One of the negative manifestations of the economic crisis is the reduction of jobs, which has led to fewer job opportunities for young people, especially those who have served their sentences in educational institutions.

Among the specific causes of juvenile delinquency at the present stage of society, the catastrophic situation in the organization of leisure time for children and youth in their place of residence stands out. Many children's institutions and organizations have ceased to

exist, and their premises have been leased to commercial structures.

The aggravation of the problems of family dysfunction against the general background of poverty and constant hardship, the moral and social degradation that occurs in families lead to extremely negative consequences. Among minors from dysfunctional families, the intensity of crime is particularly high. In these families, drunkenness, drug addiction, prostitution, lack of any moral foundation, elementary culture flourish. Specialists of various sciences quote impressive figures when they talk about minors suffering from mental illnesses that do not exclude and exclude sanity. Mental disorders in children are to a large extent the result and legacy of the corresponding behavior and life of their parents - alcoholics, drug addicts. Some combinations of mental disorders and socio-psychological deformations of personality can be largely explained by the fact that the reasons for the pathological development of the personality of minors are rooted in the asociality and immorality of their parents. Violence against each other and against their children flourishes in these families, and as a direct consequence there is a rapid increase in extremely dangerous violent crimes committed by adolescents and even children. Cruelty begets cruelty.

Juvenile delinquency is very latent. Some studies show that even before the first conviction, juveniles manage to commit several crimes. This creates an atmosphere of impunity. The inevitability of punishment, the most important means of preventing criminal behavior, is not guaranteed.

The existence of causes and conditions that contribute to juvenile delinquency does not mean the fatal inevitability of their committing crimes. These causes and conditions can be regulated, neutralized and eliminated to a certain extent. In this regard, an important role is played by general and individual prevention - a system of preventive measures applied by state bodies, including law enforcement bodies, in relation to minors who commit crimes [3].

Cases of crimes committed by minors constitute a special category of criminal cases. The issues of neglect and delinquency among minors are regularly discussed at meetings of the City Prosecutor's Office, at meetings of the Coordinating Council of Law Enforcement Agencies. There are special programs for the prevention and suppression of juvenile delinquency.

It should be noted that the most striking feature of juvenile crime is its increasingly organized, group character, i.e. juveniles form groups to commit robberies, thefts, burglaries and other crimes.

According to the Department of the Prosecutor's Office of the city of Astana, "... in the 12 months of 2015, the specialized interdistrict juvenile court of the city of Astana considered 45 criminal cases against 88 persons in the main court proceedings (in 2014 - 67/138).

In 22 criminal cases, convictions were handed down against 54 minors (in 2014 - 41/86), 4 minors were sentenced to actual imprisonment, 44 were sentenced to restriction of liberty, 5 were given suspended

sentences. 23 cases against 34 persons were closed due to reconciliation with the victims.

The latter mostly commit crimes of mercenary orientation (Articles 188, 191 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan), the causes of which are domestic insecurity, material problems, lack of control by parents and educational institutions, which in turn contributes to the commission of crimes for profit [4].

In January-April 2020, 655 minors were prosecuted in Kazakhstan, which is 31.3% less than in the previous year (954 cases).

If we talk about the age of juveniles prosecuted, 82.6% of them are 16-17 years old, and another 17.4%

Количество несовершеннолетних, привлечённых к уголовной ответственности. Январь-апрель | ед.

Расчёты Ranking.kz на основе данных Комитета по правовой статистике и специальным учётам Генеральной прокуратуры РК

The growth of juvenile crime in Kazakhstan for 2022 was 8%. In January-May of the current year 574 minors committed criminal offenses in the country - 8.1% more than last year. Among them 38 minors committed misdemeanors and 536 - felonies. 254 committed crimes of medium gravity, 225 committed serious crimes, 44 committed minor crimes and 13 committed very serious crimes. For comparison, in the same period of 2021 there were 531 juveniles among those who committed offenses, minus 34.9% for the year [5].

Crime is a socio-legal phenomenon that includes crimes committed in a given territory over a period of time and is characterized by quantitative and qualitative indicators.

The source of information for the state legal statistics is the Committee on Legal Statistics and Special Accounts under the Procurator's Office of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which collects, processes, accumulates, summarizes and updates information in the sphere of state legal statistics and keeps special accounts of subjects of legal statistics and special accounts.

The number of registered crimes is the number of revealed and officially registered socially dangerous acts stipulated by criminal legislation.

Depending on the nature and degree of danger to the public, crimes are divided into crimes of low, medium, high and especially high gravity.

Juvenile delinquents are children and adolescents between the ages of 14 and 17 who have been officially registered by law enforcement bodies and for whom criminal proceedings have been initiated.

Children brought to criminal responsibility - children and adolescents between the ages of 14 and 17 against whom an order has been issued to bring them to justice.

Juvenile delinquency is the totality of crimes committed by juveniles who are fourteen years of age at the time of the offense but under eighteen years of age.

are 14-15 years old. Of the total number of minors prosecuted, there were only 60 girls (in January-April 2019 - 59 girls).

425 of those involved were underage students (in the previous year - 617 students, annual decrease of 31.1%). There were 221 unemployed and out-of-work minors among those involved in criminal proceedings (in the same period last year - 320 young people, a decrease of 30.9% year-on-year). The number of juvenile offenders involved in criminal proceedings was 78, compared to 146 in the previous year (minus 46.6%).

The crime rate is the number of registered crimes per a certain number (usually 10 thousand) of inhabitants of a given district, region, republic. To determine the prevalence rate of crimes among minors, the denominator of the formula includes the number of persons aged 14 to 17 inclusive.

The structure of crime is characterized by the percentage ratio (specific weight) of the number of certain types of crimes to the total number of registered crimes. These data make it possible to determine at the expense of which crimes there are changes in the qualitative characteristics of crime.

Crimes committed by minors or with their complicity, total: 2018 - 994; 2019 - 650; 2020 - 873; 2021 - 529. 873; 2021 - 529, including: especially serious crimes in 2018 - 3; 2019 - 5; 2020 - 6; 2021 - 2, serious 2018 - 87; 2019 - 01; 2020 - 04; 2021 - 61, murder or attempted murder 2018 - 3; 2019 - 5; 2020 - 7; 2021 - 1; intentional infliction of grievous bodily harm 2018 - 4; 2019 - 4; 2020 - 0; 2021 - 0; robbery 2018 - 19; 2019 - 36; 2020 - 54; 2021 - 18; theft 2018 - 568; 2019. - 385; 2020 - 49; 2021 - 54; extortion 2018 - 1; 2019. - 6; 2020 - 6; 2021 - 2; fraud 2018 - 21; 2019. - 31; 2020 - 54; 2021 - 6; unlawful possession of a motor vehicle or other vehicle without intent to steal (theft) 2018 - 45; 2019 - 62; 2020 - 0; 2021 -1; illegal acquisition, transfer, sale, storage, transport or carrying of weapons, ammunition, explosives and explosive devices 2018 - 17; 2019 - 22; 2020 - 15; 2021 -13.

As practice shows, the cultural and educational level of most juvenile delinquents is significantly lower than that of their peers.

In the total mass of juvenile delinquency, the share of group crimes is high.

Criminal groups refer to small antisocial groups. Small means a small social group whose members are united by a common activity and are in direct, stable personal communication with each other, which is the basis for the emergence of both emotional relations in

the group (sympathy, dislike, indifference) and special group values, their norms of behavior [7, 58].

In recent years there has been a process of consolidation of groups of minors with illegal behavior. The process of subordination of at-risk youth groups to organized crime is actively underway. The social base for the replenishment of these groups is expanding at the expense of the unemployed, minors engaged in small business, as well as those who have returned from imprisonment and have not found a place in life, teenagers from low-income and impoverished families.

Recognition of the influence of social conditions, contradictions in the development of society on the nature of moral formation of the individual is a crucial factor in explaining the unlawful behavior of minors.

According to the world's leading criminologists, the welfare of young people from early childhood should be at the heart of any program to prevent juvenile delinquency.

It is the implementation of the basic provisions of the Declaration of the Rights of the Child, adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1959, concerning the early prevention of juvenile delinquency, general prevention and the prevention of juvenile recidivism.

According to Professor S.I. Kurganov, "...the majority of crimes are committed in the sphere of leisure. Unlike adult crime, juvenile delinquency is dominated by group crime: from half to 3/4 of the crimes are committed in a group (depending on the type of crime).

Naturally, juvenile crime was more serious than adult crime: 3/4 of the crimes committed by juveniles were serious or very serious. However, after qualified theft (which is the most frequent crime) was transferred to the category of medium serious crimes in October 2002, this figure decreased by more than 1.5 times.

For juveniles, it is difficult to objectively assess the rate of recidivism because in many cases a new conviction occurs after the age of 18: a new crime is committed as a juvenile and a new sentence is served in an adult correctional facility..."[8,64].

Crimes committed by juveniles are a signal to society that there are shortcomings in the moral education of the younger generation. The success of moral education depends on many things:

- On the creation of a healthy moral atmosphere both at the level of society and in individual collectives and families;

- on an organic combination of mass and individual work with people;

This task is all the more important because we are talking about the formation of citizens of a state governed by the rule of law, who themselves are called upon to create laws, ensure their implementation, improve legislation, and participate in the management of state and social affairs.

Juvenile delinquency, which is widespread on a significant scale, requires decisive, vigorous and targeted measures for its prevention. To this end, it is necessary to constantly improve the forms and methods of work of law enforcement bodies, to ensure their priority recruitment and material and technical supply in an appropriate manner. General and individual preventive measures applied by law enforcement

bodies to eliminate circumstances and conditions conducive to juvenile delinquency play a fundamental role in solving these tasks.

The effectiveness of this activity depends to a large extent on how these measures are grounded in current legislation in conjunction with psychology and pedagogy [9,50].

The recidivism rate for minors is not high, about 7%. However, while a person who has already been convicted of an intentional crime (legal recidivism) has a much lower rate of recidivism than an adult, the commission of a new crime by a minor who has already committed a crime (recidivism in the criminological sense) is an extremely common phenomenon. It is typical for juveniles to commit multiple episodes of theft, robbery, and assault; often less serious crimes are followed by the commission of more serious crimes. Up to 70% of juveniles convicted of acquisitive crimes had committed multiple crimes at the time of being brought to criminal responsibility.

Crime statistics in recent years show a "rejuvenation" of crime. The same is true of juvenile crime: the proportion of 14-15 year olds among those who have committed crimes is about 20%, according to sample data.

According to research data, there is a correlation between juvenile delinquency and organized crime: at least 10% of participants in organized groups and criminal associations are under the age of 18. However, official statistics claim that minors account for only about 0.5% of the total number of people who commit crimes as part of organized groups and criminal associations [10,150; 11,20]. Involvement in criminal activities at a young age closely links young offenders to the criminal environment, which influences personality and behavior, shapes the individual's value system, and thus pre-determines the future course of life.

Criminological research of the characteristics of juvenile delinquency, as well as the personality of a juvenile delinquent, is necessary not only for the development of effective preventive measures (prevention), but also for the improvement of the state policy of combating crime in general. It is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of adolescence, as well as the real possibilities of state bodies, families and public organizations in work with teenagers and youth. Differentiated and individual approach should be implemented in relation to any category of offenders, but it is especially important in relation to those who commit crimes at a young age.

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